

CONSULTANCY REPORT

Biocultural Conservation in Higher Education: Organizational Review and Consultation

**UNIVERSITY OF FLORIDA
TROPICAL CONSERVATION AND
DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM**

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Illustration by Nick Bezio

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Preface

The Tropical Conservation & Development Program (TCD) at the University of Florida has a long history of community-based conservation and working in partnership with professionals, practitioners, and forest communities throughout the tropics. We have learned that when forest and riverine peoples take a lead role in strategies and actions to protect traditional livelihoods and manage landscapes and resources, outcomes for both people and nature are better.

Biocultural conservation offers a set of theories and experiences that can strengthen TCD's approach, but also challenges us to be more open to plural ways of knowing, base our work on more equal partnerships with Indigenous and other traditional peoples, and ensure that our work contributes to positive impacts. With these challenges and opportunities in mind, we are undertaking a series of reviews and consultations to better understand the concept of biocultural conservation, how it can be effectively implemented, and – especially – the role of academia in supporting front-line conservationists to achieve biocultural conservation.

In this report, we are sharing findings and reflections from consultations with leading academic programs. The report provides a brief summary of the vision, approaches and experiences of these programs, and attempts to identify lessons and best practices that can guide future work by TCD and other academic programs who wish to pursue this agenda.

We are extremely grateful for the openness and generosity of each of these programs and those leaders who shared their experiences and reflections with us. We are truly inspired by their commitment and innovative approaches. We thank the Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation and the UF Office of Research, which provided funds for this report.

In sharing this report, we seek to promote increased awareness and recognition of these important initiatives. We recognize that the challenge of biocultural conservation requires long-term engagement with continuous learning and adaptation. UF's Tropical Conservation and Development Program aims to be a collaborator and supporter of this process. We look forward to continued dialogue and mutual learning.

Bette Loiselle

Director, Tropical Conservation and Development Program
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Introduction

The purpose of this preliminary desk study was to explore the institutional landscape of higher education that contributes to biocultural conservation. More specifically, TCD would like to:

- (a) identify the leading education and research programs that support the application of community-based (especially bioculturally-based) conservation strategies through education, research, and/or non-degree training programs, and
- (b) document best practices and experiences among leading institutions that promote biocultural conservation.

Program selection

The selection of leading programs in biocultural conservation was initiated with a Boolean Google search using the following keywords: biocultural conservation AND program OR training. From the initial result we discarded all sponsored websites (sites that paid money to rank higher); selected the first 20 sites that legitimately ranked high; and discarded four repeat entries, one job recruitment site, and the TCD/GIA site. From the original 20 organizations, we used 14 for our study (Appendix 1 - Boolean Search). To this list we added an additional 13 programs identified as potential leaders in biocultural conservation from our ongoing literature review and consultation of TCD and other partners. We thus selected a total of 27 programs to be reviewed (Note: program selection is biased toward English speaking organizations since (1) we used English words in the Google search, and (2) we added additional organizations that TCD was most familiar with, most of which were based in the USA).

These 27 programs were later subdivided into two subgroups:

Higher Priority for Analysis (Appendix 2)

Comprises 15 organizations: 10 Universities, 3 museums/botanical gardens, and 2 NGOs. The 10 Universities were given higher priority for analysis because they offer graduate training and/or research in biocultural conservation. A few non-university biocultural conservation organizations were included because they are leaders in the field of biocultural conservation and/or have a strong partnership with universities.

Lower Priority for Analysis (Appendix 3)

Comprises 12 organizations: 5 Universities, and 7 NGOs. These 5 Universities were given lower priority for analysis because they offer only undergraduate training in biocultural conservation or did not emphasize a biocultural approach.

1. Initial program reviews from published information

Each of these 27 programs was assessed using information published in the organization's websites and if possible published literature and public talks. For each program we compiled the following information:

- Type of program: research, degree granting and/or non-degree granting
- Specific questions about biocultural approach. Is the program:
 - Conducting research that is participatory and solution-oriented?
 - Co-producing and incorporating other non-western ways of knowledge?
 - Collaborating and forming partnerships with community organizations, NGOs and/or regional universities?
- Students:
 - Student profile
 - Recruitment method
 - Student support
- Degree-granting program:
 - Top skills students are expected to have after graduation
 - What is in place to teach these skills
 - Curriculum design: length of the program, course requirements, problem solving experiences, collaboration requirements
 - Extracurricular training, experiences, service
- Non-degree-granting program:
 - Training and capacity building

Foci of Biocultural Conservation Programs

The information published on organization websites reveals a great spectrum of foci in the programs working on biocultural conservation. Here are a few examples of organizational foci and work (Table 1). The complete list of organizations that were reviewed and the information collected about each of them can be found in Appendices 2 and 3.

TABLE 1: Biocultural Conservation Program Areas, Representative Organizations

PROGRAM AREA	REPRESENTATIVE ORGANIZATION	NOTES
Graduate Education and Research	University of North Texas (UNT) / Sub-Antarctic Biocultural Conservation Program	Partnership of UNT and Universidad Magallanes, Chile for graduate student training and research in biocultural conservation. High volume of publications, more here
Graduate Professional training	Colorado State University	Masters of Conservation Leadership. Trains professionals using experiential learning, interdisciplinary instruction, and applied approaches. More here
Research	Florida International University (FIU)	Tropical Rivers Lab (Dr. Elizabeth Anderson’s Lab) and other units in FIU to advance transboundary biocultural landscape in the Amazon. More here
Undergraduate Education	University of Washington: Doris Duke Conservation Scholars Program	Promote biocultural conservation. Two-summer and yearlong course work (distance learning) for undergraduate students. More here
Public Education	Terralingua	Publish Langscape Magazine to educate the public on the value of biocultural diversity. They offer many other resources here
Community Capacity Building	One Planet	Empower Indigenous and traditional communities to develop community-based solutions to manage and conserve their biological and cultural resources. More here

In the following sections, we provide an overview of each of the 27 organizations, starting with universities having specific education programs on biocultural conservation, followed by the other universities, and concluding with the other organizations: museums, botanical gardens and NGOs. In each section, the higher priority organizations are presented first.

Universities: Biocultural Graduate Training Programs (and research)

We identified four universities that have major, dedicated programs for biocultural conservation. [There are other programs that offer graduate training on biocultural conservation, but the information is not always accessible on their website. Not all of them use the term biocultural to define their programs.] Table 2 below and the following text summarizes the information for two traditional degree granting programs:

- (1) SUNY College of Environmental Science and Forestry - Indigenous Peoples and the Environment, and
- (2) the University of North Texas - Sub-Antarctic Biocultural Conservation Programs,

and two professional Master's degree programs:

- (3) Colorado State University - Master of Conservation Leadership, and
- (4) University of Guelph - Master of Conservation Leadership.

TABLE 2: Biocultural Graduate Training Programs

Program	Website	Solution driven	Knowledge Co-production	Collaboration	Knowledge taught (mandatory courses, except suny esp)	Skills taught
SUNY ESF M.S., M.P.S. and Ph.D. in Indigenous Peoples and the Environment	https://www.esf.edu/academics/graduate/indigenous-environment.php	yes	Yes, most of the time	yes	Support courses (Footnote 1): - Sloan seminar (Footnote 2) - Indigenous issues in the environment - Native people's lands and cultures - Field ethnobotany - Traditional ecological knowledge - Corals Conservation and Colonialism / Tropical Coastal Ecology (field Method collaboration) - Biocultural restoration (seminar) - Knowledge integration (seminar) - Indigenous-led conservation and stewardship (past course)	-collaboration -innovation in environmental thinking -use of traditional knowledge and western science
University of North Texas Sub-Antarctic Biocultural Conservation Master's	https://chile.unt.edu/ AND http://catalog.unt.edu/preview_program.php?catoid=18&pooid=6787&returnto=1867	yes	yes	yes	-Subantarctic Biocultural Conservation -Environmental Ethics -Master's Thesis: research needs to be performed in Subantarctic region in South America	No information on skills
Colorado State University Master of Conservation Leadership	https://warnercnr.colostate.edu/hdnr/conservation-leadership/	yes	yes (Footnote 3)	yes	-Systems Thinking and Biodiversity -Conservation Governance -Ecosystem Services -Conservation Leadership (<i>interdisciplinary understanding, leading groups and facilitating discussions</i>) -Spatial Methods -Collaborative Conservation -Multi-level Views of Conservation -Conservation Field Methods -Conservation Leadership (<i>business, management, and communication</i>) -Capstone Project	-leadership skills -collaboration techniques to bring together diverse stakeholders -communication tools -innovative methods for achieving conservation goals
University of Guelph Master of Conservation Leadership	https://geg.uoguelph.ca/mcl	yes	yes	yes	-Indigenous Knowledge Systems and Governance Models & Residency 1 (Footnote 4) -Conservation Past, Present and Possible (focus on governance) -Conservation Biology for Professionals -Residency 2: Leading (Footnote 5) -Leadership Assessment and Development -Public Communications and Engagement -Partnerships in Conservation (partnership skill building) -Residency 3: Innovation (conservation tools and technology) -Conservation Tools and Technology -Conservation in Working and Private Landscapes -Final Learning Portfolio (Students plan and execute a project)	-strategic planning -conflict resolution -team building -Indigenous engagement -evidence-based decision making -partnership development -communication

Table Footnotes: (1) These courses support Sloan Scholars. Sloan Scholars are Native American students pursuing MS and PhD degrees supported by the A.P. Sloan Foundation. The courses are not mandatory, but most Sloan Scholars take them (Mx. Sarah Howard, *personal communication*). Many of the courses were developed by Robin Wall Kimmerer. Courses are trying to fill gaps in knowledge. (2) The Sloan Seminar is a professional development skills course and is mandatory for Sloan Scholars. (3) Students are trained to co-produce knowledge. The student's project tend to involve co-production of knowledge with community, NGO, or government agency partners. (4) Face to face learning and lectures from Indigenous knowledge holders and scholars. (5) Takes place with an Indigenous partner organization/Nation.

SUNY College of Environmental Science and Forestry - Indigenous Peoples and the Environment

SUNY College of Environmental Science and Forestry M.S., M.P.S. and Ph.D. in Indigenous Peoples and the Environment is led by the renowned professor and writer Dr. Robin Wall Kimmerer. The courses in the program were developed or co-developed by Dr. Kimmerer whose work emphasizes braiding together traditional western science and Indigenous knowledge and perspective (see her best-selling and award-winning 2013 book [Braiding Sweetgrass](#)). Students in this program work in close collaboration with ESF Center for Native Peoples and the Environment, and their work focuses on biocultural restoration. SUNY ESP partnered with the A.P. Sloan Foundation in 2019 to create The Sloan Indigenous Graduate Partnership (Sloan Scholars, or SIGP Scholars) to support Indigenous graduate students pursuing STEM degrees. This scholarship program provides tuition remission, stipend, and other benefits. Sloan scholars are required to participate in the Sloan seminary that offers academic and professional development support. Courses at SUNY-ESP “support their development as scholars but also as Indigenous environmental scientists from more of a professional development standpoint” (Mx. Sarah Howard, *personal communication*). Sarah also noted that their program has a shared research agenda and a formal agreement between the Center and the [Haudenosaunee Environmental Task Force](#).

University of North Texas - Sub-Antarctic Biocultural Conservation Programs

University of North Texas/Sub-Antarctic Biocultural Conservation Master’s Program is a research-education-conservation program led by Dr. Ricardo Rozzi, and is a partnership between University of North Texas, Universidad de Magallanes, Chile and others. Dr. Rozzi is the most prolific author on biocultural conservation (Rozzi 2013, Rozzi et al. 2006, Rozzi et al. 2018). The program produces a large number of publications on biocultural conservation, a list can be found [here](#). The training program requires two courses, one in biocultural conservation and another in ethics. The research project has to be carried out in the Sub-Antarctic region and given the emphasis of the program it is very likely that it will lead to the co-production of knowledge and the incorporation of different forms of knowledge.

Colorado State University - Master of Conservation Leadership

Colorado State University / Master Leadership Program is a 1.5 year-long Master’s program. The first two semesters are devoted to mandatory courses, the summer is devoted to a collaborative, multidisciplinary, solution-based project (capstone project) and one additional semester is devoted to finishing and presenting the summer project. The

Program also offers a variety of extracurricular activities to foster experiential and project-based learning such as (1) immersion week where students forgo classes and they have the opportunity to immerse in a topic, meet experts, stakeholders, and/or carry out fieldwork and (2) Friday field activities or workshops. This professional program is solution-oriented. The course work prepares students to work as “consultants” and the capstone project is the platform to apply the knowledge and skills learned.

University of Guelph - Master of Conservation Leadership

University of Guelph / Master of Conservation Leadership (MCL) is a 2-year hybrid Master’s program. Most courses are taken online except for three Residency courses. Two of these residence courses involve learning from Indigenous elders or organizations. This program works in close collaboration with Conservation through Reconciliation Partnership (see below), an NGO co-led by five Indigenous leaders and two academics from University of Guelph (Drs. Robin Roth and Faisal Moola), who are also leading this professional Master’s graduate program. The MCL Program uses a pedagogy called [“Two-Eyed Seeing”](#) (a concept created by Albert Marshall, Reid et al. 2020), and focuses on place-based education (Endnote 1). The program operationalizes the concept with equity in mind. Biocultural conservation features prominently in this Master’s program, in undergraduate courses (e.g. [GEOG*3210 - Indigenous-Settler Relationships in Environmental Governance](#)) and Dr. Moola’s research program (Dr. Moola’s *personal communication*). Dr. Moola’s lab attract primarily Indigenous students (Dr. Moola *personal communication*)

Additional information for these programs can be found in the in-depth interviews in Part 2 of this report, as well as in Appendix 2.

Universities: Additional Biocultural Efforts

Some Universities do not offer formal graduate or professional training in biocultural conservation, yet their efforts in the field are very noteworthy and relevant. These are some of the insights I gathered:

University of Hawai‘i

Biocultural conservation training at the University of Hawai‘i is dispersed across different departments/programs. This reflects the great awareness and breadth of the biocultural field but may make it hard for students to find courses and peers (Dr. Rachel Dacks, *personal communication*) and for researchers to work together and collaborate. To provide a space for these efforts to interact, Dr. Christopher Dunn (now at Cornell

University) led the effort to establish a Center for Biocultural Studies at the University of Hawai'i which culminated in the [Biocultural Initiative of the Pacific](#), “a knowledge center and network linking scholars, instructors and students who share the common goal of thinking holistically to enhance understanding of biocultural systems.” This initiative has been responsible for teaching a graduate [seminar in biocultural diversity and conservation](#), providing funding for community-based work of graduate students, and organizing occasional lectures. The Initiative has been less active in the last few years since the pandemic (Dr. Rachel Dacks, *personal communication*). The [Hawai'i Institute of Marine Biology \(HIMB\)](#) at the University of Hawai'i is leading important biocultural efforts. HIMB hired the late [Dr. Eleanor Sterling](#) as their director to advance biocultural work (2022 - February 2023); HIMB houses the He'eia National Estuarine Research Reserve ([He'eia NEER](#)) that works to implement biocultural restoration of key habitats for future generations. Dr. Kawika Winter, a Biocultural Ecologist at HIMB, is the Director of He'eia NEER. The University of Hawaii's continued effort in this field is also reflected in the recent hiring of Dr. Rachel Dacks (January 2024) as Assistant Professor of Biocultural Stewardship in the Department of Natural Resources and Environmental Management.

Cornell University

Dr. Christopher Dunn is working to make the Cornell Botanic Gardens a hub, meeting, and collaboration space, for all the people at Cornell working on bioculture that so far have worked in relative isolation: Linguistics, Music, Arts, Science. This biocultural diversity initiative has captivated people and given them a sense of the greater value and worth of the work they're doing. Dr. Dunn hopes to be able to create a Biocultural Center at Cornell. Dr. Dunn gave special recognition to his collaboration with Dr. Karim-Aly Kassam (Kassam et al. 2022, Kassam et al. 2023). Dr. Kassam is doing research on biocultural conservation nationally and internationally and he has a strong teaching and mentoring program. His vision for the role of education and paradigm change can be seen [here](#). Dr. Kassam's work is also a great example of a biocultural approach to development and climate change issues. More about Dr. Kassam [here](#).

Additional information from in-depth interviews with Drs. Rachel Dacks (University of Hawai'i) and Christopher Dunn (Cornell University) is included in Part 2. We also prioritized the following universities but could not secure an interview for more in-depth analysis. The limited information that is on their websites is summarized in Appendix 2:

- Wageningen University,
- Indiana University,
- Yale University.

Florida International University provided answers to our questions by email after this report was written, see Endnote 2.

The following universities were identified but not selected for in-depth analysis. Information from their websites is summarized in Appendix 3:

- University of Washington. Doris Duke Conservation Scholars - undergraduate
- Stanford University. Bing Overseas Studies Program - undergraduate
- Oregon State University. Anthropology Department - undergraduate
- University of Colorado, Boulder. Master's of the Environment - does not emphasize a biocultural approach
- University of California, Santa Barbara. Bren Master's of Environmental Science and Management - does not emphasize a biocultural approach

Some additional universities that were not included in our study but could be investigated in future studies are presented, with contact information, in Appendix 4.

Non-Universities - Biocultural Research and Action Programs

In addition to the organizations of Higher Education, there are many organizations pursuing research and/or action with a biocultural conservation focus. Table 3 below is a list of these organizations and some highlights about each of them. Additional Information for these programs can be found in Appendices 2 and 3.

TABLE 3: Biocultural Research and Action in Non-University Organizations

Program	Website	Location	Note	Highlights
The Center for Biodiversity and Conservation at the American Museum of Natural History	https://www.amnh.org/research/center-for-biodiversity-conservation	USA	Dr. Ana Luz Porzecanski, Director	Focus: research with Indigenous and local communities. Biocultural approach led mostly by the late Eleanor Sterling, former Chief Conservation Scientist, who implemented a culturally grounded approach to management and conservation. Developed biocultural conservation-development training material for practitioners. Formal biocultural conservation education is very thin (Endnote 3).
The Keller Science Action Center at the Field Museum	https://www.fieldmuseum.org/departments/keller-science-action-center	USA	Drs. Alaka Wali Corine Vriesendorp, and Paula Ungar, researchers	Focus: Rapid Inventories of vast landscapes with a high potential for conservation. These rapid biological and social inventories are grounded in a biocultural approach and have helped conserve 28.9 million acres since 1999, more here . The biocultural approach is well elaborated in Wali et al. 2017 and Pitman et al. 2021 . Mission: Translating science into action to build a brighter future rich in nature and culture.
National Tropical Botanical Garden (NTBG)	https://ntbg.org/	USA, Hawai'i	Dr. Nina Rønsted, Director	Focus: biocultural conservation is one of their focuses. Work to restore health and function of socio-ecological systems that have been sustainably managed by native Hawaiians. Mission: to enrich life through discovery, scientific research, conservation, and education by perpetuating the survival of plants, ecosystems, and cultural knowledge of tropical regions.
Legado Initiative	https://www.legadoinitiative.org/	Kenya, Mozambique, Peru	Dr. Tita Alvira, Global Director of Thriving Futures	Focus: Collaboration with Indigenous peoples and local communities (IPLCs) in places important for biodiversity to ensure they have the tools, resources, and partnerships they need to design and implement solutions of their choosing that benefit both their communities and landscapes—an outcome called Thriving Futures. Mission: is to build a locally-led system for sustained collective action that fosters agency, adaptability and resilience for meeting current and future challenges—such as those brought on by climate change. The work revolves around legacy as an activator for individual and collective change.
The Conservation through Reconciliation Partnership	https://conservation-reconciliation.ca/	Canada	Dr. Faisal Moola, co-leader	Focus: development of (1) appropriate biocultural indicators (selected by Indigenous people) for conservation, (2) Indigenous Protected and Conserved Areas (IPCA). Leadership: 5 Indigenous leaders and two university-based academics from the University of Guelph. Mission: transform the conservation sector in Canada.
Terralingua	https://terralingua.org/	USA/Canada	Dr. Luisa Maffi, Co-founder and Director	Focus: public education on biocultural diversity. Use diverse media. Has an ongoing Biocultural Diversity Education Initiative, more here Mission: Promoting understanding and appreciation of the vital value of the world's biocultural diversity for the thriving of all life on earth.
Amazon Conservation Team (ACT)	https://www.amazonteam.org/	USA	Co-founders Mark Plotkin (USA) and Liliانا Madrigal (C Rica)	Focus on the Amazon (Colombia-Surinam-Brasil-Peru) Uses GIS tools heavily to protect territory and claim Indigenous land's rights. Recording of oral history. Mission: ACT partners with Indigenous and other local communities to protect tropical forests and strengthen traditional culture.
WCS (Wildlife Conservation Society)	https://www.wcs.org/	USA	Monica P. Medina, new President and CEO	Focus: biodiversity research, conservation and education (zoos and aquariums). Provide scholarships for graduate work on conservation, research fellowships, and conservation leadership programs. Mission: WCS saves wildlife and wild places worldwide through science, conservation action, education, and inspiring people to value nature.
Oak Spring Garden Foundation	https://www.osgf.org/bccf	USA	Dr Peter Crane, President (Senior Research Scientist at Yale School of the Environment)	Focus: heirloom vegetables and fruits. Provide grants for early-career plant conservation scientists. One of the purposes is to save biological diversity of edible plants in the Appalachian and Virginia Piedmont. Mission: dedicated to inspiring and facilitating scholarship and public dialogue on the history and future of plants.
One Planet	https://www.oneplanet-ngo.org/	Peru	Dr. Michael Gilmore, President (George Mason University).	Focus on Majjuna group NE Peru. Produced movie Guardians of the Forest that shows the fight of the Majjuana people to stop a road through the heart of their territory. Mission: We partner with Indigenous and traditional communities to build a more sustainable, empowered, and just future by working towards community organization and well-being, biocultural conservation, and sustainable development.
Alianza Sierra Madre	https://alianzasierramadre.org/en/350-2/	Mexico	Not sure if it is very active	Focus on biocultural conservation, human rights and community well-being. Mission: ¡La lucha sigue! Que nuestra lucha y resistencia nos permita seguir brotando en nuestro territorio.
Biocultural Conservation Institute (BCI).	https://bioculturalconservation.org/	Kenya	Not very active now	Focus on Maasai Indigenous communities. Mission: empowering local communities to connect to and protect their native wildlife through education, research, and livelihood enhancement.

2. In-depth interviews with leaders of priority programs

Based on the initial review of these 27 programs, we prioritized a group of 15 that were organizations of Higher Education pursuing biocultural conservation work at the graduate level, or organizations with a strong partnership with universities (Appendix 2). I gathered additional information by interviewing 7 program leaders representing 8 out of the 15 programs. I could not secure interviews with the remaining 7 despite multiple attempts.

When interviewing program leaders, I attempted to answer the following questions:

1. What are the necessary knowledge, skills and competencies needed to advance biocultural conservation and how can universities provide for them?
2. How are universities considering these skills and knowledge? Could you provide examples of:
 - a. Research that is participatory and solution-oriented
 - b. Co-production of knowledge and the incorporation of diverse knowledge systems
 - c. Collaboration and partnership
3. What is the role of academia in advancing biocultural conservation? What is missing? What would you like to see?

I was able to interview:

- Dr. Michael Gavin (Colorado State University),
- Dr. Rachel Dacks (University of Hawai'i),
- Dr. Christopher Dunn (Cornell University),
- Dr. Faisal Moola (University of Guelph and The Conservation through Reconciliation Partnership),
- Mx. Sarah Howard (Center for Native Peoples and the Environment, SUNY College of Environmental Science and Forestry),
- Dr. Ana Porzecanski (Center for Diversity and Conservation at The American Museum of Natural History),
- Dr. Tita Alvira (Legado Initiative, previously Field Museum)

Skills and competencies needed to advance biocultural conservation

The following set of skills, knowledge and competencies are those that the scientists interviewed for this work shared with me. Students interested in conservation biology need more than just ecological and management courses, they need:

Knowledge:

- Interdisciplinary training
 - Courses in epistemologies, place-based methods
 - History, and interpretation of history based on who is writing it
 - Politics and Economy
- Colonial science and decolonization methodologies (see The Kūlana Noi'i or contact Dr. Rosie Alegado at Hawai'i University)
- Ethno-studies (ethnography, ethnomusicology, ethno-linguistics, etc.)
- Law (or lawyers)
- Understanding how conservation has impacted Indigenous and local communities (oftentimes in a very negative way)
- Legacy of colonial conservation policy on Indigenous peoples
- Indigenous protected areas (Endnote 4)
- Social sciences methodologies

Skills:

- Know how to be humble (can teach by modeling)
- Know how to collaborate ethically
- Awareness of different ways of thinking and knowing and its contribution
- Awareness of cultural diversity, or cultural understanding
- Ability to resolve and facilitate social processes
- Understanding of the role of political and economic forces, as well as justice issues
- Ethics (not be patronizing, know how to build relationships of trust)
- Experience working with local communities
- Critical examination of *status quo* conservation policy
- Patience with time frames
- Conflict resolution
- Participatory methods
- Ability to focus on process ("If you want to go fast, go alone, if you want to go far, go together")
- Ability to understand the interlinkages between nature and people's dependence on landscape.

Please also see the [report](#) of the North American Conference on Conservation Biology Interactive Session on Conservation Literacies (Groom et al. 2022). The skills and knowledge this group discusses are for “conservation,” however many of the participants in this team are “biocultural conservationists,” thus the distinction between conservation and biocultural conservation is not very relevant in this case.

Additional needs in the fields:

- Lawyers: One of the people interviewed (Dr. Dunn) sees the need to have lawyers interested in the field. Terralingua has a lawyer specialized in Indigenous rights and aboriginal law on their board, supporting this idea.
- Arts and the humanities: Some recognize the need to bring the arts and the humanities into the field “because through the written word, the spoken word, through music, through sculpture, we inspire people” (Dr. Dunn, edited).
- Linguistics: Linguistic faculty are especially important, they understand rarity and endangerment, and they have a superb understanding of the natural landscape where language develops (Dr. Dunn).
- Direct access to local decision makers, and local knowledge through a community-oriented pedagogy. Need to build partnerships with Indigenous or local communities in order to be able to implement conservation solutions (Dr. Moola)
- Critical examination of *status quo* conservation policy (colonial model of conservation): “In order to better understand the importance and the need for biocultural community-led conservation which offers an alternative, and I would say one that is not only effective, but also is socially just.” (Dr. Moola)
- Amplifying and uplifting Indigenous and local peoples, to participate in conservation, e.g. [Indigenous Protected and Conserved Areas or IPCAs](#) (Dr. Moola)
- Learn to move at the speed of trust. It is challenging to manage the time frame that it takes to do biocultural conservation – i.e. to build trust and have relationships in place is not as fast as we would like. “The truth is things are urgent and so it’s a real challenge.” (Dr. Porzecanski)

Role of Academia in Biocultural Conservation and the future of the field

Interviewing biocultural conservation leaders to explore this question was very insightful. Here is a summary of their views, hopes and insight.

Dr. Michael Gavin, Colorado State University.

The role of academia is to establish collaboration with NGOs, organizations and/or communities to change the paradigm of biodiversity conservation. Academia needs to help shift away from one worldview and a cookie cutter approach towards conservation that embraces (1) multidisciplinary collaborations, and (2) multiple worldviews. Academia's role is also to amplify the voices of different cultures. This is happening already to some degree (e.g. [new White House guidelines](#) that aim to include traditional ecological knowledge in Federal environmental decision making) but more is needed: (1) Need to amplify voices, (2) Need representation of these voices, (3) Need to build more partnerships, and (4) Need to include different worldviews.

Dr. Rachel Dacks, Hawai'i Institute of Marine Biology, University of Hawai'i.

The role of Academia is (1) training the next group of scholars in this biocultural space, (2) translating the knowledge that communities have into policy and governance (when requested and/or desired by communities), (3) building reciprocal relationship-partnerships with communities. She affirmed that "we learned from them, we should also give back," including in terms of financial compensation. Rachel emphasizes that training the next generation of scholars in interdisciplinary and biocultural approaches is very important. In Hawai'i there is a disproportionate number of non-Hawaiians in government, in university, etc. Many are in leadership roles and are often trained in old conservative ways. The university's role is to do a better job of recruiting and mentoring members from our Indigenous and local communities, so that their knowledge, practices, and worldviews are better represented. There is a university-wide initiative to become a Native Hawaiian place of learning (<https://manoa.hawaii.edu/nhpol/aloha-aina/>). As part of this initiative, different departments/groups at UH are developing their unique ways to implement this plan. The graduate program in Marine Biology where Rachel works developed a 2-week mandatory class for all incoming students called: MBI0 600 - Kūlana Noi'i: Introduction to Place-based Research Methodologies in Hawai'i. [Kūlana Noi'i](#) is a recent publication that provides an ethical framework to explore reciprocal, place-based research methodologies (more [here](#), or contact Dr. Rosie Alegado).

Dr. Christopher Dunn, Cornell Botanic Gardens, Cornell University.

(1) Universities, especially Land-Grant Universities like Cornell, need to begin to grapple with their history of occupation of and disposition of Native American land by being the beneficiaries of the Morrill Act. Universities need to come to terms with their history and find some ways for reconciliation and restitution. (2) Universities need to embrace a biocultural approach. Cornell is doing cluster hires, a movement that reflects a more transdisciplinary approach to research. Embracing the biocultural approach gives greater meaning and value to the research because we are all embedded in nature. (3) Universities are a powerful voice, often viewed as thoughtful, non-political and without hidden agenda and ought to use it. Missing still is the comfort level to reach out to Indigenous neighbors, ‘we’d say in Hawai’i, let’s talk story.” University leaders need to reach to Indigenous leaders and ask them to sit down and talk and talk many times, and build a relationship of trust. Some Universities are already doing this, e.g. University of Wisconsin-Madison ([here](#)), University of California-Berkeley ([here](#)).

Dr. Faisal Moola, University of Guelph and The Conservation through Reconciliation Partnership.

His research team has shown that the term biocultural diversity has emerged but it has not been operationalized (see systematic literature review by Lukawiecki et al. 2022). Universities need to form the next generation of scholars that are embedded in an anti-colonial approach to conservation, or conservation through reconciliation: reconciling with historical and contemporary harm done to Indigenous communities by colonial structures, including academia, but also the self-transformation that takes place when instructors, students and faculty work directly with Indigenous people (Endnote 5). Most countries in the world signed the 2022 Convention on Biological Diversity. This agreement mandates that by 2030 we uplift Indigenous knowledge systems, alternative Indigenous conservation, governance, biocultural diversity, etc. (<https://www.cbd.int/article/cop15-cbd-press-release-final-19dec2022>). We need to operationalize this mandate at the national level and universities will need to start radically reforming the way they think about conservation. We will need (1) more research, (2) more capacity building, (3) development of curricula to implement the global biodiversity framework. His dream is for biocultural diversity to appear in all courses (environmental sciences, political sciences, climate change, etc), and in order to do that we need to create a space to make sure the average professor becomes aware of the new mandate to operationalize conservation solutions in partnership with Indigenous people. We also need a change of paradigm by amplifying and supporting Indigenous people. “I think that’s the change in the paradigm, because I think that if you lift up Indigenous people in terms of their land rights, their

governance, their knowledge systems, then by default you are going to create the landscape where biocultural diversity will flourish.”

Mx. Sarah Howard, Center for Native Peoples and the Environment, SUNY College of Environmental Science and Forestry.

Students trained in their program have a challenging time at the university level: (1) encounter bias against traditional ecological knowledge within Academia: research questions and methodology are not always accepted; (2) lack of understanding of biocultural approach, and unfamiliarity with interdisciplinary work. They also encounter difficulties after graduation: (1) getting jobs within white-led conservation organizations or academia, (2) getting grant support. Overall the great challenge is that the paradigms and protocols of academia are often not well aligned with the kinds of research projects our students want to do in the realm of biocultural conservation and restoration, specifically community, partnerships and collaborative work. This in turn affects progress towards graduation and funding. What is needed? There needs to be decolonization of academic science. It is not enough to allow students to do biocultural conservation research, we need also to affirm and offer positive support (grants). Grant money is often not aligned with the frames of biocultural work.

Dr. Ana Porzecanski, Center for Biodiversity and Conservation (CBC) at the American Museum of Natural History (AMNH).

Dr. Porzecanski worked very closely with the late Dr. Eleanor Sterling at the AMNH and possesses a wealth of institutional memory about Eleanor’s biocultural approach to conservation that she led at the museum (Endnote 6). Dr. Porzecanski thinks that teaching conservation needs to change to embrace more social dimensions and systems lenses, social sciences, and biocultural approaches. The feedback that emerged from the educational exchange at the North American Conference of the Society of Conservation Biology in 2022 (Interactive Session: [Conservation literacy as interwoven literacies: a sharing and learning session](#)) can be useful to biocultural conservation since there is so much overlap (Groom et al. 2022). Dr. Porzecanski invites TCD to join this effort if interested in the subject. In addition, we need to think about the role of Academia and to do that we need to rethink the incentives and motivations that are provided to academics; if academics are evaluated by their teaching evaluations and their papers then they will not spend as much time working with communities. Work in Academia should also be more interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary; academia is still working in silos, making it hard for even students to work across disciplines: asking interdisciplinary questions also requires interdisciplinary methods. We need to “have literacy in all of these inquiry domains and work together. And respect that... Both I and many of my colleagues feel

that the state of the world and the crises that we face make it very hard to just do business as usual as an academic.” The role of academia to advance biocultural conservation can be as a bridge between traditional knowledge holders and institutions of governance. These institutions want evidence-based solutions and academia needs to provide that evidence working with the traditional knowledge holders. Ana suggests asking Chris Filardi about the role of Academia and Museums in bridging this knowledge. Ana also kindly provided a list of additional resources on biocultural conservation available on the CBC website (Endnote 7).

Dr. Tita Alvira, Legado.

Dr. Alvira is the Global Director of Thriving Futures at Legado. She believes that Universities (1) need to give students opportunities to understand holistically, (2) give students the opportunity to learn how to carry out participatory research and involve the local knowledge holders in their work, (3) need to create interdisciplinary and intercultural dialogue. What is missing? Academia is not doing a great job at translating knowledge to local users and decision makers (policy, politics). Universities have the power to validate different forms of knowledge. The co-creation of knowledge, the translation, and the diffusion of this knowledge has the power to influence politics and education and improve social-political processes. For example, Tita participated in Conservation International's effort to carry out rapid assessment ([RAPs Rapid Assessment Program](#)). This program was very successful in translating information for local people and decision makers (with the people, for the people).

Concluding Remarks.

Main lessons and take-aways from this exercise.

The biocultural approach to conservation is not new. In 1988, the anthropologist Dr. Darrell Posey (1947-2001) organized the First International Congress of Ethnobiology (Belém, Brazil) giving rise to what is known as the Declaration of Belém (Posey and Dutfeld 1996). The “[Declaration of Belém](#)” outlined “the responsibilities of scientists and environmentalists in addressing the needs of local communities and acknowledged the central role of Indigenous peoples in all aspects of global planning” thus guaranteeing the conservation of biological and cultural diversity. The concept “biocultural diversity” was the result of conversations between the linguist and anthropologist Dr. Luisa Maffi and the conservation biologist Dr. David Harmon in 1995. These conversations gave rise to the NGO Terralingua in 1995 and the international conference “Endangered Languages, Endangered Knowledge, Endangered Environment” (1996) that established biocultural diversity as a new field. The results from this conference were published in the book “On Biocultural Diversity: Linking Language, Knowledge, and the Environment” (Maffi 2001). (<https://terralingua.org/who-we-are/our-history/>). The term biocultural conservation became perhaps best known by Dr. Michael Gavin’s highly-cited 2015 paper “Defining biocultural approaches to conservation.” As the field expanded, one of the key people in its expansion was the late Dr. Eleanor Sterling. Dr. Sterling led conservation programs in the Center for Biodiversity and Conservation (CBC) at The American Museum of Natural History (AMNH) (1999-2021) and the Hawai’i Institute of Marine Biology (HIMB) at the University of Hawai’i at Mānoa (2022-2023). Her influence can be seen at the CBC biocultural approach to conservation, HIMB vision and planning, and most notably in her research work, the training and mentoring of an outstanding number of students and mentees (Betley et al. 2023), including Ana Porzecanski at AMNH, Rachel Dacks at UH-Mānoa, Chris Filardi at Nia Tero, and many others. More on her contribution can be found [here](#) and in Betley et al. 2023.

My exploration of the field of biocultural conservation in Higher Education highlights that this is a growing field gaining value and support from international agreements, national policy, and the public. Biocultural conservation has the potential to change the way we approach many of the environmental challenges of this century. Internationally, the 2022 Convention on Biological Diversity agreement aims to conserve and manage 30% of the world’s lands and waters by recognizing Indigenous and traditional territories and practices by 2030 (<https://www.cbd.int/article/cop15-cbd-press-release-final-19dec2022>). Nationally, the Biden-Harris Administration recognized Indigenous knowledge and released new Indigenous knowledge guidelines for Federal Agencies (<https://www.whitehouse.gov/ceq/news-updates/2022/12/01/white-house-releases-first->

[of-a-kind-indigenous-knowledge-guidance-for-federal-agencies/](#)). The general public has learned about the field through Dr. Robin Wall Kimmerer's popular 2013 book "Braiding Sweetgrass: Indigenous Wisdom, Scientific Knowledge, and the Teaching of Plants". The book has been on The New York Times Paperback Nonfiction Best Sellers list since February 2020.

Universities are also embracing and leading this biocultural approach, as seen most notably to my knowledge at the University of Hawai'i at Mānoa with (1) its initiative to become a Native Hawaiian place of learning, an initiative that started in 1986. (<https://manoa.hawaii.edu/nhpol/aloha-aina/>), (2) creation of the Biocultural Initiative of the Pacific (<http://manoa.hawaii.edu/biocultural/>) with its long list of faculty and students working on biocultural issues. Dr. Christopher Dunn, currently the Director of the Cornell Botanic Gardens, has been one of the leaders of this initiative since he was at the University of Hawai'i and is currently pursuing similar efforts at Cornell University (*personal communication*). Hawai'i seems to be at the center of a transformation, and biocultural conservation and the University of Hawai'i has been central to it, in Sam 'Ohu Gon and Kawika Winters' words "[A Hawaiian Renaissance That Could Save the World](#)".

Universities have, in the opinion of many of the people I interviewed and learned about, an important role to play in biocultural conservation. One of the roles that was highlighted by many is the University role in helping to change the predominant paradigm of conservation from a white-led 'colonial conservation' to one that is centered on collaboration and the co-production of knowledge. This work could be accomplished by elevating/amplifying the voices of local and Indigenous knowledge holders, and by giving representation to those voices.

Traditional universities have had a hard time playing a relevant role in solving social and environmental problems. Bureaucracies, insularity, elitism, rewards systems and other factors have limited their potential (Beyond the Academy 2022). This is also what the interviews show when discussing what is missing to advance biocultural conservation. In general, many agree that the paradigms and protocols of academia are often not aligned with biocultural research approaches:

- (1) academia is still working in silos thus making interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary work hard to pursue,
- (2) academic incentives to pursue interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary work are often lacking,
- (3) timelines are challenging (it takes time to build relationships to pursue community-based research),
- (4) there is a lack of interdisciplinary methodology,

- (5) there is a lack of curricula to prepare the next generation of biocultural conservationists, and
- (6) there is a lack of efforts to build partnerships and dialogue with local and Indigenous communities, addressing the history of occupation and harm by colonial structures, including academia.

The University educational role is essential in changing the current paradigm. Universities can and should prepare the future leaders in the conservation field by helping them gain the skills and knowledge that are needed for this alternative paradigm as identified in this report: cultural awareness, humility, understanding of different ways of knowing and knowledge, colonial science and decolonization methodologies, etc.

Universities can also use their power as independent institutions to amplify and be a bridge between the traditional knowledge holders and policy makers. (“Universities are a powerful voice, often viewed as thoughtful, non-political and without hidden agendas and (they) ought to use it.” Dr. Christopher Dunn). The co-creation of knowledge, the translation, and the diffusion of this knowledge has the power to influence politics and education and improve social-political processes (Dr. Tita Alvira).

Lastly, biocultural conservation is not competing with WHAT many view as the great challenges of our time (climate change, species extinctions, etc). Biocultural conservation is an inclusive and equitable approach, and as such it simply shows the world HOW we could do conservation. This approach is clearly summarized by the National Tropical Garden in Hawai'i as “a progressive approach to conservation that recognizes and honors the intrinsic relationships between nature and humanity, and builds conservation programs that are founded in cultural values and aligned with community priorities.” This has been TCD's approach while focused on conservation and development in the tropics since the nineties. It would be great to see TCD partner with other institutions of higher education in the field.

Suggestions and Follow-up

In the light of what I learned through this desk study and interviews,

1. I suggest interviewing Drs. Luisa Maffi, Karim-Aly Kassam, and Josephina Chambers: [Dr. Luisa Maffi](#) at Terralingua. Dr. Maffi is one of the pioneers in the field of biocultural diversity and conservation. Given what we know now, Terralingua should have been selected as High Priority for analysis and interview. The author is already working on scheduling an interview with Dr. Maffi in July and plans to include her insights in a future publication. Dr. Maffi knows Prof. Rick Stepp at TCD with whom she collaborated in the context of Terralingua projects early on (*personal communication*) and she is very happy to make time for a conversation. She might be another potential partner for TCD.

[Dr. Karim-Aly Kassam](#) at Cornell University (Department of Natural Resources and the Environment, and the American Indian and Indigenous Studies Program). I discovered about his work a little too late but he is doing marvelous research on biocultural conservation nationally and internationally and he has a very profound insight about the role of education.

[Dr. Josephina Chambers](#) at Utrecht University (Netherlands). Josephine is the author of the 2021 paper “Six modes of co-production for sustainability” and has been awarded the [Dies Natalis of Wageningen University in 2022](#) for her course 'Transformative Research for Global Social-Environmental Challenges'. Course information [here](#).

2. There are also a number of universities and programs/labs that would be worth exploring that were not included in this report; for more details see **Appendix 4**.

- National Center for Scientific Research (CNRS), [Dr. Joaquin Claudet](#) (France)
- The University of British Columbia (Canada)
- George Mason/School of Integrative Studies, [Dr. Michael Gilmore](#) (founder of NGO One Planet)
- [Stacy Jupiter](#) from WCS (worked with Eleanor Sterling in the Solomon Islands)
- Chris Filardi (recommended by Ana Porzecanski. He used to be at the AMNH. Created [Nia Tero](#) which is a well funded organization, they fund guardians of land to secure territorial rights). cfilardi@niatero.org
- List of Participants in the publication Beyond the Academia by Keeler and Locke 2022

Endnotes

(1) Place-based education in biocultural conservation by Dr. Faisal Moola (transcript edited for clarity)

“So the Masters of Conservation Leadership (MCL) facilitates place-based education. It's impossible to give undergraduates that place-based experience and I've been really struggling. The main thing I've been trying to do is give them access to Indigenous knowledge holders on video and audio guest lectures. The reading list is heavily dominated by Indigenous community scholarship, but it doesn't give them anything like the experience of actually being on land, which is really critical in my mind to do biocultural research.

Well, and then for my other graduate students who are outside of the MCL program, they spend vast amounts of time embedded within the community. So they are living and working and doing research with Indigenous guardians. So Indigenous guardians are people that work in the Indigenous community, who are given the responsibility of stewardship over the Territory. So the students are embedded with the guardians, and so they're at every moment utilizing traditional ecological methods of analysis and then, at the same time, they are with the guardians, and learning directly from the guardians, as well.”

(2) Response by Dr. Simone Athayde at FIU to our questions on the Role of Academia in advancing biocultural conservation, and ongoing biocultural conservation efforts at FIU (via email)

What is the role of Academia in advancing biocultural conservation?

Academia can play a fundamental role in biocultural conservation. Universities, research institutes and other academic organizations are on the forefront of knowledge creation and dissemination, and that also includes conceptualizations, practices and science-policy connections. However, biocultural approaches to conservation can be considered to be in their infancy regarding formal academic structures, curricula, as well as theoretical and methodological approaches, including inter- and transdisciplinary engagements. Inter and transdisciplinary engagements are fundamental to enable epistemological intertwining and innovations regarding theoretical, methodological and applied aspects of biocultural diversity. We know that there are several obstacles for the integration of knowledge across disciplinary fields as well as non-academic knowledge, including Indigenous and local knowledge. Nevertheless, despite these several obstacles, which may be institutional, political, epistemological, and structural, the biocultural diversity approach also creates opportunities for crossing disciplinary and knowledge borders in a more practical way. The concept is broad enough to include problems and case-studies from around the globe, from urban to rural contexts, and from food to forests and rivers.

What is missing? What would you like to see?

As I mentioned, there is much more to be done regarding enhancing formal education and training on Biocultural Diversity in academic spaces. In my opinion, some main issues are:

- *Lack of formal curriculum design, guidance and consistency around approaching biocultural diversity in academic spaces.*
- *Lack or need for multiple voices (epistemological pluralism) and inclusion of Indigenous peoples and local communities in shaping biocultural diversity in theory and practice.*
- *Need to promote interdisciplinary opportunities for connection between biophysical, social scientists, and Indigenous peoples and local communities in knowledge co-production around biocultural diversity - this could be done around special events, workshops, institutes, forums, or other initiatives.*
- *Lack of academic structures and incentives toward interdisciplinary engagement around biocultural diversity.*
- *Lack/ need to recognize and promote multiple languages - connecting linguistic diversity to biological and cultural diversity in academic spaces. Normally, only social scientists and biophysical scientists engage in interdisciplinary research, with lack of engagement of linguists.*

I like to see more of the topics above, specifically greater diversity and epistemological pluralism approaching biocultural diversity theory, research and practice in academic spaces.

I tried to figure out what FIU had regarding biocultural conservation research and education and did not see a formal training program except a few courses. FIU is, however, doing biocultural conservation (your lab, Elizabeth, etc, more [here](#)), and students in those labs are likely learning the skills and knowledge to carry this kind of work. Is this correct?

Yes, correct. We are approaching biocultural diversity in our classes, labs (my Lab's name is Biocultural Diversity and Governance Lab), and projects. Although there is no formal program named as such, Biocultural diversity is a core concept in our Amazonian Biocultural Riverscapes Project in the Amazon. I also approach it in my methods course as you noted below, including classes dedicated to read about and learn from Indigenous and local knowledge - connected to the idea of Decolonizing Conservation

I found training in Elizabeth Anderson lab and the Tropical Conservation Institute: IRES Wildlife Conservation Training Program in the Caribbean. Anything else?

Yes, FIU's Global Indigenous Forum, in which I actively participate, has strived to include Indigenous peoples in knowledge production and decolonizing academic knowledge through several events and initiatives. More information here: <https://indigenous.fiu.edu/>

(3) Biocultural conservation education at American Museum of Natural History by Dr. Ana Porzecanski (transcript edited for clarity)

"I think the education piece hasn't really been formal education. There has been education, what I would call guidance materials and professional development materials for practitioners mostly." Biocultural education is very thin. "We've been wanting to do this, but the truth is that the experts in this were so busy running these funded research projects and writing these other products that we just didn't have the time to generate teaching modules on them."

"The last thing I wanted to say is that in my experience often when we run into geographers we see that the work they're doing is often biocultural conservation. And so I think there is an interesting fuzziness with geography programs that should be explored."

(4) Teaching. Biocultural approach to Protected area creation and management by Dr. Faisal Moola (transcript edited for clarity)

"Typically Western science takes precedence over Indigenous knowledge systems, or there's an inequity in terms of access to resources and funding, and such. But I think purposely all that ends up doing is reinforcing the existing power dynamics which is disenfranchised, Indigenous peoples, to begin with."

So in the protected areas example, a way of rectifying those power dynamics is that when we talk about protected areas, we talk not about conventional protected areas, we talk about Indigenous protected and conserved areas. The students are learning about protected areas, which is a very well established conservation solution, but it is different from how protected areas are thought about traditionally. These are Indigenous-led, Indigenous-established, Indigenous-managed conservation areas. So the outcomes of those conservation areas and the rationale and motivation for those Indigenous productive areas is reflective of the community and their priorities. It may be we are establishing this protected area as an Indigenous protected and conserved area, using biocultural approaches, not just to protect the habitat of this endangered animal, but also to improve the health and well-being of community members, to provide and facilitate intergenerational transfer of ecological knowledge between elders and youth, to provide healing, to provide areas where people can harvest medicinal plants, so you understand all of the biocultural elements are optionalized in a much more successful way, because the power dynamics in the hands of the community to design that solution in the way that meets their priorities."

(5) Forming the next generation of biocultural conservation scholars by Dr. Faisal Moola (transcript edited for clarity)

“We have excluded Indigenous people from the way in which knowledge is being transferred to young people and these young people are being trained, and then they are being recruited into the institutions that are given the responsibility of conserving land and water and wildlife but they have no access to Indigenous people, no access to Indigenous knowledge, no access to Indigenous territory, and so they come equipped in a very deficient manner. You know, and then at the end, somebody is told, okay, now you have to think about Indigenous people, but they have no worldview or interest in it, because they were never exposed as a younger person.”

(6) Biocultural approach to conservation by Dr. Ana Porzecanski (transcript edited for clarity)

“Eleanor would always say, biocultural approach to conservation is all about process. It is not about doing this or that, or using one word or another, it is about respecting a process that starts with and is grounded in local culture practice and needs” (Francisca’s note: emphasizes the work on HOW, not on the WHAT e.g. climate, change, restoration, etc)

(7) Dr. Ana Porzecanski kindly pointed out to us these additional resources on biocultural conservation that are available on the Center for Biodiversity Conservation website of the American Museum of Natural History (AMNH) but are not easy to find,:

- <https://www.amnh.org/research/center-for-biodiversity-conservation/research-and-conservation/biocultural-conservation> (Search for: The CBC’s Biocultural Approach AND Implementing Culturally Attuned Monitoring and Reporting Indicators: very helpful guidance for practitioners, governments)
- <https://www.amnh.org/research/center-for-biodiversity-conservation/convening-and-connecting/biocultural> (Biocultural convenings)
- <https://www.amnh.org/research/center-for-biodiversity-conservation/convening-and-connecting/biocultural/dialogues-for-action-on-biological-and-cultural-diversity/2018-action-group-on-knowledge-systems-and-indicators-of-wellbeing> (2018 Action Group on Knowledge Systems and Indicators of Wellbeing, results from two gatherings with Indigenous experts)
- <https://www.amnh.org/research/center-for-biodiversity-conservation/resources-and-publications/nature-culture-indicators-resources> (Nature-Culture Indicators and Knowledge Systems Resource Directory; search the Nature-Culture Resource Directory or click: [191 summaries](#);, the directory is the result of the 2018/2019 Action groups, but it has been hard to maintain)

- <https://nerrsciencecollaborative.org/project/pascua20> (Cultural Ecosystem Services in Estuary Stewardship and Management. Pua'ala Pascua and Eleanor Sterling led this project, and it is a collaboration between Hawaiian and Alaskan Indigenous and cultural practitioners in natural resource management)
 - <https://nerrsciencecollaborative.org/resource/methods-pilot-summary-cultural-ecosystem-services-estuary-stewardship-and-management> (Report 1)
 - <https://nerrsciencecollaborative.org/resource/expanding-and-deepening-application-cultural-ecosystem-services-estuary-stewardship-and-0> (Last report)

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